

LEARNING SKILLS OF MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS

Ms. Pratibha Verma, Ph.D. Student

Dr. Shashi Malik, Professor

Faculty of Teacher Education, V. M. L. G. College Ghaziabad

Abstract

The aim of this research work is to study the learning skills of school students. Learning skills dimensions as Critical Thinking Skills, Creativity Thinking Skills and Communication Skills are studied. All middle school students who are studying in Bulandshahr district rural area are considered as target population. Using random sampling technique, 100 (50 boys and 50 girls) students were shortlisted as sample. Descriptive survey method is used. The objectives of present study are to explore learning skills and compare learning skills of boys and girls students. Self-made learning skills assessment tool was used in research. The t-test was computed to determine the significance difference in learning skills between girls and boys students. The girl's students were found better than their count parts in all three learning skills.

Key words:- Learning skills, Critical Thinking Skill, Creativity Thinking Skill and Communication Skill, Gender

INTRODUCTION

Learning is the process of knowledge and understanding new contents, change behaviours and preferences, improve skills, values and attitudes. Learning Skills are the abilities and competencies to acquire the knowledge, skills and attitude; to process and retain the enable learners to solve problems, communicate effectively with others and adapt to new situations and challenges. With the beginning of the 21st century, the whole world has witnessed an era of intense transformation in all areas. In this modern period, whole education system aims to develop skills in students. These skills are addressed as 21st Century Skills or Learning Skills or Transversal Competencies.

All learning skills as critical thinking skills, creative thinking skills, collaboration skills, communication skills, Information Media technology literacy skills, Artificial intelligence skills are to be developed in modern time. Various researchers talk about 21st century skills developing strategies and improving performance of students. For development of 21st century skills in individuals, research organization and educational organizations are working according to the rapid changes and complexities of present time. Central Board of Secondary Education, Delhi defined 21st century skills in handbook as, "These are the skills critical thinking skills, creative thinking skills and communication skills" that are required by an individual for his/ her holistic development so that he/she can contribute to the progress and development of his society/ nation and world." In this handbook, four types of learning skills are considered (4Cs): Critical Thinking, Creativity & Innovation, and Collaboration & Communication skills.

Onoshakpokaiye (2021) found that learning skills significantly influence students' performance in mathematics at the secondary school level. Good learners tend to perform better than those with weaker learning abilities in mathematics. *Higgins et al.* (2007) reviewed the impact of learning skills on the development of learning capabilities.

Roya and Murthy (2016) found that critical thinking has a positive effect on academic achievement among secondary and senior secondary school students. *Sodhi and Gill* (2020) summarized that there is a strong relationship between critical thinking, academic achievement, and intelligence. *Joshi and Sheela* (2021) also discovered that students with high critical thinking abilities tend to achieve better academically, whereas those with low

critical thinking abilities generally perform worse. *Zhang* (2022) noted that critical thinking skills help learners find their courses more meaningful. Furthermore, *Joshi and Sheela* (2021) indicated that critical thinking ability is positively correlated with problem-solving ability and achievement in science.

Reddy et al. (2015) that there was significant impact of gender, locality of residence and class of study on non-verbal creativity among high school students. Boys were high in their non-verbal creativity than girls; students hailing from urban areas were secured higher non-verbal creativity scores when compared with rural students and the students studying different classes differed in their non-verbal creativity.

Bezeria et al. (2022) found that creativity has a strong relationship with intelligence and learning skills. *Hasan* (2017) noted that intelligence was positively and significantly related to all four dimensions of divergent thinking: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. Furthermore, all dimensions of divergent thinking were positively and significantly related to both verbal and non-verbal creativity. *Yadav and Kaushal* (2021) found significant differences in all dimensions of creativity and overall creativity between males and females. They also observed significant differences between genders regarding vocational interests, adjustment, and family climate.

Guclu (2016) found that women tend to excel in self-expression, communication, and recognizing various stimuli, a trend that becomes evident from infancy. This research indicates that girls begin speaking earlier than boys. Additionally, girls tend to learn reading and writing skills in school earlier than their male counterparts and are generally more successful in learning foreign languages. These emotional expressions may be influenced by the gender roles that are culturally expected. In this perspective, various researches are focused on different skills and abilities of school students but no one is centred towards key learning skills exploration. Thus, researcher is dedicated here to explore key learning skills and study gender differences of middle school students in learning skills.

Objectives of the study

For the present study the following objectives were drawn:

1. To study learning skills of middle school students.
2. To compare the critical thinking skills of girls and boys students of middle school.
3. To compare the creative thinking skills of girls and boys students of middle school.
4. To compare the communication skills of girls and boys students of middle school.

Hypotheses of the study

Following hypotheses were tested in present study:

H₁: There is no significant difference in critical thinking skills of girls and boys students of middle school.

H₂: There is no significant difference in creative thinking skills of girls and boys students of middle school.

H₃: There is no significant difference in communication skills of girls and boys students of middle school.

Research design

The study focuses on the students of government middle schools affiliated with the UP Board in the Bulandshahar district of Uttar Pradesh. A random sampling technique was employed to select the participants. Initially, the researcher compiled a list of schools in the Bulandshahar district, and then used a lottery method to randomly select schools in rural areas. The sample for this research consists of 100 students, all aged between 12 and 14 years. Specifically, the sample includes 50 girls and 50 boys from the 8th grade, chosen from various schools. The researcher utilized a descriptive survey

method for this study. To assess the students' learning skills, a self-made learning skills assessment tool was implemented.

Result and discussion

1. To thoroughly investigate the learning skills of eighth-grade students, a comprehensive Learning Skills Assessment test was conducted involving 100 participants. All three key skills - critical thinking, creative thinking, and communication were analyzed using descriptive statistics to gain valuable insights.

Table 1.0: Descriptive Statistics related to Learning Skills of middle school students

S.N.	Dimension of Learning Skill	Mean	Mdn	Mode	S. D.	Kurtosis	Skewness	Range
1.	Critical Thinking Skill	14.07	12	9	5.79	-1.19	0.38	24
2.	Creative Thinking Skill	113.56	113	112	27.30	0.71	-0.12	141
3.	Communication Skill	33.21	32	34	8.74	0.92	0.05	50

Table 4.1 presents a detailed descriptive analysis of various learning skills. The mean score for critical thinking skills is 14.07, which falls within the average range according to the norms of the test. This indicates that students demonstrate average critical thinking skills. Similarly, the mean score for creative thinking skills is 113.56, also reflecting average performance. In terms of communication skills, the mean score for students is 32.21, which, according to the norms, categorizes them as having average communication skills, as scores between 28 and 38 are considered average.

The statistics presented in Table 4.1 clearly demonstrate that the data is normally distributed, as the skewness is well within the acceptable range of -1 to +1. Furthermore, the kurtosis falls between -3 and +3, further confirming the normality of the distribution.

Table 4.2: Categorical analysis of Learning Skills scores of middle school students

Learning Skills	Level	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Critical Thinking Skill	Very High	2	2
	Above Average	32	32
	Average	33	33
	Below Average	31	31
	Very low	2	2
Creative Thinking Skill	Very High	5	5
	Above Average	21	21
	Average	51	51
	Below Average	17	17
	Very low	6	6
Communication skill	Very High	3	3
	Above Average	22	22
	Average	53	53
	Below Average	20	20
	Very low	2	2

According to Table 1.1, the learning skills and their dimensions include critical thinking skills, creative thinking skills, and communication skills. Each dimension is categorized into five levels: very high, above average, average, below average, and very low. Out of 100 students in middle class, only 2 students (2%) fall into the category of very high

critical thinking skills, while 32 students (32%) are categorized as having above average critical thinking skills. Additionally, 33 students (33%) fall into the average category, 31 students (31%) into below average, and 2 students (2%) are classified as having low critical thinking skills. The results indicate that most students fall into the above average, average and below average categories for critical thinking skills.

Out of 100 students in middle class, only 5 students (5%) fall into the category of very high creative thinking skill. Meanwhile, 21 students (21%) are categorized as having above-average creative thinking skill, 51 students (51%) have average creative thinking skill, 17 students (17%) are considered below average, and 6 students (6%) fall into the low creative thinking skill category. As shown in Table 1.1, the highest numbers of students belong to the average and below-average categories in creative thinking skill.

Out of 100 students in middle class, only 3 students (3%) fall into the category of very high communication skills. Additionally, 22 students (22%) have above-average communication skills, while 53 students (53%) possess average communication skills. Furthermore, 20 students (20%) are categorized as having below-average communication skills, and 2 students (2%) have low communication skills. This data indicates that the majority of students fall into the average and below-average categories for communication skills.

Therefore, it can be concluded that most students have average or below-average skills in all dimensions of learning skills.

- To compare the critical thinking skills of girls and boys students of middle school following hypothesis was verified:

H₂: There is no significant difference in critical thinking skill girls and boys students of middle school.

Table 2: Mean, S D Values on Critical thinking skills of girls and boys students of middle school

Groups	Value of critical thinking skills			Degree of freedom	t-value	Level of significance
	N	Mean	S.D.			
Girls	50	15.7	5.507	98	2.988	Significant at 0.01
Boys	50	12.18	5.812			

Table 2 shows that calculated-t value is 2.988, which is higher than the table t-value 2.63 at degree of freedom 98 and level of significance 0.01. It is clear that difference between means of both groups is significant at 0.01 level. So, null hypothesis H₁ is not accepted for research. It can be said that there are gender differences when critical thinking skills studied. On the basis of higher mean value of girls (15.7), it can be said girls are good critical thinkers in comparison to boys.

- To compare the creative thinking skill of girls and boys students of middle school.

H₃: There is no significant difference in creative thinking skill between girls and boys students of middle school.

Table 3: Compare the Creative thinking skill of girls and boys students of middle school

Groups	Value of creative thinking skills			Degree of freedom	t-value	Level of significance
	N	Mean	S.D.			
Girls	50	121.12	26.498	98	3.042	Significant at 0.01
Boys	50	105.12	27.987			

Table 3 shows that calculated t-value, mean and Standard Deviation. They found that value of calculated-t is 3.042; it is upper than the table t-value 2.63 at degree of freedom 98 and level of significance 0.01. It is clear that difference between means of both groups is significant at 0.01 level. So, null hypothesis H₁ is rejected for research. On the basis girls and

boys of means scores are not equal in creative skill. Gender is affected on creative thinking skills. Creative thinking skills of Girls are better than their counter part.

4. To compare the communication skill of girls and boys students of middle school. H₄: There is no significant difference in communication skill between girls and boys students of middle school.

Table 4: Compare the communication skills of girls and boys students of middle school

Groups	communication skills			Degree of freedom	t-value	Level of significance
	N	Mean	S.D.			
Girls	50	39.22	6.822	98	9.752	Significant at 0.01
Boys	50	26.6	6.596			

After data calculation result show it above table 4. Researcher found that value of calculated-t is 9.752, It is higher than the table t- value 2.63 at degree of freedom 98 and level of significance 0.01. It is clear that difference between means of both groups is significant at 0.01 level. So, null hypothesis H₁ is rejected for research. Girls and boys of means scores are unequal in communication skills. Communication skills of Girls are better than their counter part. Gender is affected on communication skills.

Finding of the study

1. The majority of middle school students demonstrate average learning skills. Analysis shows that many students are classified as above average, average, or below average in critical thinking skills. Notably, the largest group is in the average and below average categories for creative thinking skills. Furthermore, a significant number of students also fall into the average and below average categories for communication skills.
2. The girls and boys students studying in middle classes have difference on critical thinking skills. Girls are better than boys in critical thinking skill at secondary level. Female was better than male in critical thinking. (*Walsh & Hardy, 1999; Faiari et al, 2013; Supriyati & Djukri, 2021; Noverli & Cahya, 2021*).
3. The girls and boys students studying in middle classes have difference on creative thinking skills. Girls are better than boys in creative thinking skill at secondary level. *Ülger & and Morsünbül* (2016) study also support it. But according to *Lau & Cheung* (2010), boys had higher creativity scores among the primary and secondary students.
4. The girls and boys students studying in middle classes have difference on communication skills. Girls are better than boys in communication skills at middle level. *Kumar & Devi* (2018) support this research.

According to *Heijltjes et al.* (2014), learning skill is related to brain's anatomy. A male has a brain with the area of cortex working on spatial functions more so that the ability of a man to produce and process words becomes less than female. Because female has a callosum, which is four times larger than men. Therefore, man cannot focus on more work at the same time. *Fajari et al.* (2013) stated that the critical thinking process of female students is more complicated than male students because female students have reflective and rational thinking but male students have only rational thinking.

Conclusion

Learning skills play a crucial role in everyone's life. They help individuals acquire new knowledge, skills, and competencies. Research indicates that the levels of various learning skills among middle school students are often average. Most students tend to have average or below-average skills in creative thinking and communication, while their critical thinking skills fall into above average, average, and below average categories. The findings also show that girls generally perform better than boys in all learning skills, including critical thinking, creative thinking, and communication skills. Learning skills

can help differentiate between good and poor learners. Good learners possess the ability to absorb information effectively. Once a child acquires the specific learning skills needed to process, understand, remember, and apply knowledge gained in school, their learning ability significantly improves. As a result, these students gain more confidence in their abilities, experience greater success across all subjects, achieve higher scores on tests and exams, and enhance their overall intelligence. Learning skills can be continually developed and improved to help individuals accomplish daily tasks and achieve their career goals.

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